

**THE MANIFESTATION OF THE LINGUISTIC PERCEPTION OF THE
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LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECTS****Sevinch Abdumalikova Tayirovna**O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti
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Abstract. In the article, the concept of the translation process is developed as a multi-level "language game" and interpreted in the spirit of linguo-philosophical views. The author considers ineffective the views of a number of linguists who reduce the essence of the sought phenomenon only to humorous and satirical-comic forms of its manifestation. Linguistic and cultural investigation of translation as a unique phenomenological, symbolic-interpretive language game is proved by L. Carroll's examples of "nonsense" and abracadabra, burlesques and F. Nietzsche's "linguistic curiosity" and others. The discussed problem is analyzed against the background of activity-anthropocentric perception language and its functional paradigm.

Key words: language, speech activity, language games, culture of laughter, translation process, translation speech.

The speech activity of a society with Homo loquens at the epicenter of its attention is ontologically aimed at the implementation of two basic functions of the language - cognitive and communicative. She explicitly reflects the main goal-setting of the modern anthropocentric paradigm in a chronotopically heterogeneous, multi-vector linguistic continuum of the late 20th century and the beginning of the current century.

Language, as you know, is used to describe, express feelings, evaluate and suggest feelings. It can be realized in a speech statement normatively and conventionally. It performs its functions, as a rule, in postulate, declarative, symbolic-magical, aesthetic-artistic and some other forms. And if we recognize that language is the home of being, and the world of a person is limited by the framework of his language, then we should

agree that the mental, cognitive-associative space of an individual closely correlates with his communicative and activity potential. And the latter outlines the boundaries of the speech-playing field available to the individual in the environment of his linguistic existence. And in order not to be fenced off by a “wall of misunderstanding” in a given language community, he must be guided by the rules and norms “language games” characteristic of the everyday idiom of the sub-range of its speakers.

“Language games” (German Sprachspiele, English translation – language-games), as a fundamental concept and term-symbol of one of the main directions in the theory of speech activity, were introduced into active scientific circulation after the posthumously published treatise of the famous philosopher L. Wittgenstein (1889-951) under the title “Philosophical Investigations” (1953), which was repeatedly translated into different languages, including Russian.

In paragraph 23, L. Wittgenstein clearly formulates his understanding of the term “language game”, which “is intended to express the circumstance that speaking a language means acting, that is, a form of life.” He believed that there are an unlimited number of uses of the language, and they cannot be reduced to any canonical list of them. Some of their varieties he presents as follows:

- “Give orders and obey.
- Describe the appearance of an object or its dimensions.
- Create an object according to the description (drawing).
- Report an event.
- Discuss the event.
- Develop and test hypotheses.
- Present the results of the experiment in tables and diagrams.
- Write and read stories.
- Play on stage.
- Sing dance songs.
- Solve riddles.
- Make up jokes and share them.

- Solve arithmetic problems.
- Translate from one language to another - (our italics. - E.M.).
- “Ask, thank, scold, greet, pray” [Wittgenstein, 2011, p. 30-31].

It is obvious that the famous philosopher undoubtedly appears before us as the forerunner of the theory of speech acts by J. Austin and J. Searle, who practically passed over this relationship in silence.

Thus, L. Wittgenstein's “Philosophical Investigations” reveals the essence of speech activity in connection with various “forms of life”, which makes it possible to synonymously verify “language games” as “discursive games”. Note that it is no coincidence that N.D. Arutyunova is the author of the article "Linguistic Philosophy" in the LES (in which she defines a "language game" as a complete communication system that meets some “form of life”) defines “discourse” as “speech “immersed in life” [Arutyunova, 1990, p. 17, 269].

The term-concept "language game" adequately fits into the paradigmatic thesaurus of the theory of speech communication in general and the science of translation in particular. It can serve to designate integral and complete communication systems that obey their own internal rules, the violation of which leads to going beyond the limits of a particular “game”, i.e. certain speech act.

Linguists turned mainly to that side "language games", which reflects the exaggerated use "laughter" means of language with a conscious violation of the "language norm", in order to destroy the automaticity of perception of the content of the statement and the maximum possible use of the so-called "deceived expectation" effect. Thus, they unwittingly emasculated the voluminous content of the concept of “language game”, which was meant by L. Wittgenstein, limiting himself to describing comic-curious fragments of the language system.

We must pay tribute to a number of authors who have studied in detail the numerous ways of “carnivalization of speech”, which is achieved, in particular, with the help of puns, parody, burlesque, allusion, paronymization, precedent inclusions,

homonymy, etc. They see the main goal of the game in "lure - attract - distract - kill - fool" and so on. or "to besiege - to condemn - to stigmatize - to nail the addressee", etc.

There is no doubt that the goal is important, but not all-consuming in speech practice. "Laughing language games" are always either "verbal painting", or "cunning verbal craftiness", or "verbal hooliganism", widely used in texts of various functional and stylistic genres. At the same time, in works of art, the presence of "linguistic anomalies" is considered as a manifestation of a special "literary norm".

Translation of various types, genres and forms of language games is in itself a kind of speech activity, which is a unique phenomenological semiotic-interpretive language game. In other words, within the framework of the ludic concept of speech acts, we interpret the translation process as a specific type of speech activity in the field of intercultural communication, which is a multi-vector interlingual mediation with the aim of re-expressing the text of a foreign language in signs of a foreign language at the maximum achievable levels of correspondence - cognitive-heuristic, ethnopsycholinguistic, discursive-creative and some others depending on the text type of the original.

For the theory and practice of translation, the subjective opinions of translators about their work are of considerable interest, especially when it comes to comparing "their own" and the previous "foreign" translation of the same work. Thus, L. Dobroselsky speaks of the Russian translation of Philosophical Investigations in 1994 and his version in 2011 as follows: "We tried to follow the author's text as accurately as possible, which was not always possible, given the differences in the structure of the Uzbek, German and Russian languages (the translator of the English edition was in this sense much easier). It is the desire to convey the author's thought and style as accurately as possible that explains the heavy constructions that sometimes occur in our translation, and "chopped" phrases, and sentences that at first glance are not intelligible and contradict the stylistic norms of the Russian language. The same explains the vocabulary: Wittgenstein rarely resorts to technical and scientific terms, trying to operate with the words of everyday language; in addition, he often uses words

that, when translating, allegedly require “replacement according to context”, the choice of a suitable one from a number of synonyms, but here we followed the author (for example, the word “atmosphere”). The previous translation of “Philosophical Studies” into Russian (M.: Gnosis, 1994) was not so much a translation as such, but an interpretation of the author’s text (for example, what the author spoke about briefly or *nyalos*); that is why it was decided to prepare <...> a new translation of Wittgenstein's work” [Wittgenstein, 2011, p. 339-340].¹ As for the source of the original, it was taken as a basis 1997 bilingual (German-English) Oxford edition, “in which the original text in German is compared with an English translation by a student of Wittgenstein ... G.E. Anscombe.” At the same time, the translator admits that “although the German and English texts differ quite a lot in some paragraphs, in general, the presence of bilingualism greatly facilitated the translation <...>, since the philosopher’s own formulations are sometimes so figurative, abrupt and/or obscure that it is hard to understand in them, on the basis of the original alone, it would be very difficult” [ibid., p. 339]. Along the way, we note that when publishing a new corrected version, the translation should already be based on the new bilingual treatise published in 2009 [Wittgenstein, 2009].

The theoretical arsenal of the science of translation only in recent 15-20 years old, he was replenished with such promising concepts based on the original metalinguistic foundation, such as: cognitive-heuristic and discursive theory of translation, text translatology, cognitive turn in the semiosis of translation, dialectical interaction of identity and cognitive dissonance in translation process, the *aporia* of translatability-untranslatability and the conceptual-frame asymmetry of texts in FL and TL, “*skopos*”-theory and the primacy of the social order in translation practice, introspective-reflexive nature of translation consciousness and experimental testing of its phenomenological explanatory power, “language games » in interlingual mediation and game (human) model of translation, etc.

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